

Elite Healers Sports Massage is more than just a massage, it's therapy. They are setting a higher standard in the world of massage therapy. Visit the Elite Healers Sports Massage website at <https://www.elitehealerssportsmassage.com> to book an appointment or to see their hours of operation. They are setting the standards higher in an unstable world. They are a Sports Massage and Medical Massage company in New York City and their clinic is in midtown Manhattan (a.k.a. midtown in New York City). They provide recovery for athletes of all levels with Sports Massage. They also help people manage chronic muscle pain, recover from injuries, recover from surgery and help to provide muscle relief to those who just have regular muscle aches and pains by providing medical massage services as well. They are not a spa, but are closer to a physical therapy clinic in the sense that they are more treatment focused, than relaxation focused. Services include: Sports Massage Therapy, Medical Massage Therapy, Deep Tissue Massage Therapy, Swedish Massage Therapy, Thai Massage, and Chair Massage Office Events. You can book a 60, 90, or 120 minute session. You will be happy that you did!

Now that you know more about Elite Healers Sports Massage and their many services, let's talk about the benefits of a medical massage. If you're looking for a way to relieve stress and get some relief from pain, massages are an excellent option. They're also helpful for a variety of other medical conditions.

A massage therapist who is a medical massage therapist will work closely with doctors in treating health conditions such as cancer, fibromyalgia and neuropathy. This type of massage requires a prescription from the doctor.

Reduces Stress:

Medical massage reduces stress through a variety of mechanisms including decreasing heart rate, relaxing muscles and increasing the production of feel-good hormones. This also promotes the parasympathetic nervous system which is a natural reaction to stress that calms the body and mind. The stress of everyday life is a major contributing factor to many health problems including high blood pressure, depression, anxiety and increased suicide attempts. It is vital that we have a way to manage our stress and prevent it from becoming a chronic condition.

A new study shows that receiving a massage or simply allowing yourself a few minutes of downtime significantly boosts your mental and physical relaxation. It is the first time that a short-term treatment has been shown to robustly reduce stress on a psychological and physiological level by boosting the body's principal engine for relaxation, the parasympathetic nervous system (PNS).

Improves Sleep:

Massage can improve sleep by lowering stress levels, improving anxiety and decreasing pain. It also increases serotonin, a neurotransmitter that promotes feelings of happiness and relaxation, helping you drift off into sleep more easily. Research has shown that massage can increase the production of melatonin, which is important for telling your brain when it's time to go to sleep. And it can increase delta brain waves, which are linked to deep sleep.

People often have trouble sleeping because of tense muscles. This can be due to a physical job or mental stress that tenses the muscles, and it can also be a result of medical issues like arthritis. The good news is that medical

massage can help you get a better night's sleep, no matter what your reason for not getting enough rest. It can help you reduce your muscle tension, lower stress and increase the production of serotonin and melatonin to promote the best possible sleep.

Reduces Pain:

Massage can decrease pain by stimulating nerves that send pain-reducing signals to your brain. The level of pressure used in a massage has a major impact on how effective it is. A recent study conducted by researchers at the Mayo Clinic in Rochester, Minnesota, found that patients who received massage therapy while in the hospital reported a reduction in their pain levels. Using a visual analog scale, the researchers compared pain levels before and after receiving massage.

The results showed that participants reported a reduction in pain and that they felt more relaxed after their massages. Additionally, they reported a decrease in their 'substance P' levels which is a neurotransmitter that can influence pain and inflammation.

Increases Flexibility:

Medical massage can increase flexibility through a number of techniques. The increased temperature of the muscle fibres during a massage enables them to stretch out and loosen. The kneading movements within a massage encourage increased blood flow to the treatment area. The increased blood flow results in capillarisation and vasodilation of the muscle fibres which increases the temperature of the muscles.

Increased tissue elasticity improves flexibility and reduces injury. The stretching of muscles during a massage allows for full range of movement, improving performance and helping to prevent injuries in the future. Flexibility is also enhanced when a person undergoes [Sports Massage NY](#) a massage before a sport or event as the muscles are often tight and tense which can increase the risk of injury.

The therapists are trained to recognise if the person has tight or tense muscles that can be stretched during the massage and are then able to do this throughout the treatment session. The stretching and loosening of the muscles during a massage will also help to relieve pain and relax the individual, enhancing their overall health and wellbeing. Now that you know more about the benefits of a medical massage, it is time to go back to the website of Elite Healers Sports Massage out of New York City to book an appointment today!